

THE MEDICINAL ASPECTS OF PUMPKIN IN FOLK MEDICINE

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Abstract: This article provides detailed information about the types, chemical composition and healing properties of the pumpkin plant, and the medicinal properties of the pumpkin plant in various folk remedies. Useful medicinal properties of pumpkin, its nutritional value, its benefits and how to eat it are given. **Key words: properties of pumpkin, extraction of carotene, characteristics of pumpkin, varieties of pumpkin, medicinal value of pumpkin.**

Pumpkin (*Cucurbita* L.) belongs to the magnolia family (*Magnoliophyta*) section of the world of higher plants, *Magnolipsida* class, *Dilleniidae* subclass, *Cucurbitales* tribe, *Cucurbitaceae* Juss. family. The family *Cucurbitaceae* Juss. is distributed in almost all regions of the Earth and includes 800 species. There are 18 naturally growing species of this family in the flora of Uzbekistan. There are about 900 varieties of pumpkin, of which 400 varieties are suitable for consumption. Mineral content: minerals content per 100 grams. Proportion of daily requirement. Potassium 204 mg 8%, calcium 25 mg 3%, Magnesium 14 mg 4%, Phosphorus 25 mg

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Like all the blessings of our motherland, our people love to eat pumpkin from time immemorial. The variety of dishes prepared from it also reflects the importance of this blessing. A person always tries to look healthy and beautiful, pays attention to healthy eating. He seeks to know the composition of the food he consumes. The chemical composition of pumpkin is very rich in vitamins and minerals. When eating

Fig. 3. Different types of Cucurbita are shown in the photograph.

foods made from pumpkin, the body is provided with a sufficient amount of macro and microelements and vitamins[1-5]. Pumpkin contains more substances such as iodine and fluorine compared to other polys crops, and it is useful for the body. Its seeds contain up to 50% oil. The amount of vitamins A, C, B1, B2, PP, carotenoids and carbohydrates in meat is 5 times higher than that of carrots and 3 times higher than that of beef liver. Therefore, in ophthalmology, it is recommended to eat the flesh and juice of pumpkin when the eyesight decreases. Substances extracted from it prevent the growth of tubercle bacilli. Among them, vitamin B1 is involved in the metabolism of carbohydrates. Its deficiency causes diseases of the nervous system and disorders of the cardiovascular system. Vitamin B2 (riboflavin) enters the composition of various enzymes and participates in reactions in the body. In its deficiency, angular stomatitis is observed.

Vitamin V6 is involved in protein metabolism. Due to the lack of this vitamin, children develop tension of nerve fibers and dermatitis, i.e. skin inflammation. Vitamin V9 (folic acid) participates in the metabolism of proteins and choline. Pumpkin contains substances that prevent aging. It also contains vitamin E, which increases the activity of the gonads. The peel contains a lot of pectin and clechatka. Its seeds are rich in lipids, proteins, vitamins and mineral salts. Zucchini is unique because it has a positive effect on the endocrine system and improves digestion. It is also useful for overweight patients due to its low calorie content. Pumpkin juice or raw bark is used for cough and tuberculosis. Porridge made from pumpkin helps with bronchitis and lowers the temperature. Also, this polys crop is involved in the synthesis of vitamin B12. Due to its positive effect on the pancreas, the cobalt content of pumpkin participates in the formation of insulin. Experts found that people who lived a long time included pumpkin in their daily diet. After surgery, it increases the resistance of the weakened body to infections. Pumpkin is also very useful for atherosclerosis, tumors related to the cardiovascular system, kidney, liver and bladder diseases, hypertension, metabolic disorders. Autumn is the time to see today's hero the most, pumpkin. Although now we can find it in supermarkets and markets at any time of the year.

Pumpkin has great medicinal properties, we will talk about its nutritional values, its benefits for us and how to eat it. Pumpkin is a regular part of our diet, it is delicious and it is very versatile as both sweet and savory recipes can be prepared. Zucchini stands out for its orange color, one of its well-known benefits is strengthening the health of our eyes, protecting and preventing cataracts. It is rich in fiber and it helps in intestinal transit.

Nutritional properties of pumpkin Before we get into the healing properties that this food gives us, let's first tell you what it contains, because it is its components that make our body healthy. It has a lot of amino acids. How oleic, silicic or palmitic acid, It provides us with vitamin C, which is a B group of vitamins. On the other hand, the work of vitamin E or folic acid stands out.

Gives coumarins: have antioxidant properties, avoid the harmful effects of free radicals. It contains a large amount of fiber. Water: Pumpkin contains a large amount of water. It is a food with many components and nutrients that satisfy us and at the same time hydrate us. On the other hand, minerals include calcium, magnesium, manganese and potassium. By its orange color, we can tell that it is rich in beta-carotene, or the same thing as vitamin A, a type of flavonoid that is considered a natural anticancer agent. Pectin substances contained in pumpkin have a good effect on intestinal inflammatory diseases, help to remove bacteria and toxic substances from the intestine, and prevent dehydration of the body in diseases with diarrhea. At the same time, pumpkin also accelerates the removal of cholesterol from the body. Therefore, patients with heart and blood vessels (atherosclerosis, hypertension), chronic colitis and enterocolitis, severe (quick) and chronic nephritis, pyelonephritis, cholecystitis, gallstones and jaundice (hepatitis) should be included in their daily diet. it is recommended to add. Also, pumpkin is useful as a dietary food, especially for the elderly and young children. Pumpkin juice has a calming effect and improves sleep, and is a good antiemetic (also pumpkin), especially for pregnant women.

Medicinal properties of pumpkin

All these qualities become a series of very useful properties for the body. Make sure we tell you the most important ones:

It is a diuretic food and helps us remove the fluids we retain. Maintains healthy and functioning kidneys.

Because it contains fiber, it is a clean and healthy intestine. Kill parasites or possible worms. Stimulates the function of the pancreas, and also regulates the amount of sugar in the blood. The amount of antioxidants strengthens the immune system. Reduces the risk of prostate cancer. Maintains good heart health.

How to eat pumpkin It is a healthy and nutritious food, a very versatile vegetable. As you can see, you can use all the benefits of pumpkin. It can be consumed in any type of diet, since it does not make us overweight, in fact, if used in the best way, we can lose weight with it. Pumpkin contains a lot of water, about 92% water, so it is very low in calories, because 100 grams of it gives 30 kcal. It has a low protein content and is rich in carbohydrates. Harmful properties In case of kidney failure, excessive use can worsen the patient's condition. Because the removal of potassium from the body is impaired. People suffering from gastritis and peptic ulcer disease do not need raw pumpkin. This vegetable, if raw, irritates the surface of the mucous membranes. People with high acidity of gastric juice should use with caution. A healthy person can eat pumpkin freely, abundantly and with pleasure.

Pumpkin is widely used in cosmetology due to its richness in vitamins. Here are some recipes for effective face masks. If there are a lot of wrinkles, a cream mask will help. To do this, pass the pumpkin through a fine grater. Take two tablespoons of the mass, add two tablespoons of sour cream and the same amount of honey. Mix well and apply on face and neck area. Leave on for 15 minutes and wash off with warm water. Honey mask helps with deep wrinkles. Grind a medium-sized pumpkin, add a tablespoon of honey and half a lemon juice to it. Apply the mask for 20 minutes and wash off with warm water. Oatmeal crushed pumpkin mask helps to get rid of oily shine on the face. 1:2 ratio. With dry skin, you can cut the vegetable into thin rings and

put it on your face, and after 20 minutes, wash it off with milk, then dry it a little with a towel.

We can eat pumpkin in several ways: Boiled, griddle, fried, in confectionery: cakes, cookies, cakes.

Fat-free cooking options are healthier. No matter which one you choose, it tastes sweet, smooth and delicious. The shell that covers it is not edible, it is very hard and should be thrown away. You can eat pumpkin seeds, they are similar to sunflower seeds, although they are highly recommended for the treatment and prevention of prostate cancer. In the market we can find different types of pumpkin, there are many varieties, some of them are sweeter than others, but their nutritional properties do not differ. We recommend buying pumpkin slices, because those who sell the cut have already gone through the manipulation process. The fresher the fruits and vegetables are, the better. Look for nearby crops and farmers who are definitely running an eco-friendly industry in their area.

conclusion. In case of kidney and liver diseases, it is recommended to eat freshly squeezed pumpkin juice (100-200 grams per day) or 500 grams of grated meat. Pumpkin improves the motor activity of the gallbladder, and is also very useful for inflammation of the gallbladder.

Pumpkin juice cleanses the kidney and liver system and strengthens its functioning. In pyelonephritis, acute and chronic cystitis and some forms of urethritis, it is useful to eat 50 grams of pumpkin porridge twice a day. For use in hepatitis, cholecystitis, and cirrhosis of the liver: the top of the pumpkin is cut off, the seeds inside are removed, honey is filled in the space formed in the middle, and then the cut top is closed in its place like a lid. , the dough is smeared around it and kept in a dark place for 9 days. Drink 1 tablespoon of the resulting juice 3 times a day.

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